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Name: Daniel Pribula, Martin Kendra

Organisation: University of Zilina

E-Mail address: daniel.pribula@stud.uniza.sk

ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTS OF REDUCING PARALLEL RIDES IN THE SELECTED REGION

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INTRODUCTION

One way to increase the attractiveness and efficiency of public transport is to implement an integrated transport system (ITS). The main objective of ITS is to unify public and, in many cases, non-public transport services, which will increase their synergy and efficiency from the point of view of all stakeholders (Rodriguez, 2020). This public transport solution is planned to be implemented in the nearest future within the Eastern Slovakia region (Fig. 1). This region belongs to the NUTS 2 European regions, with the cities of Košice and Prešov as its centres, i.e. it is a binuclear region. The area of Eastern Slovakia is more than 15,000 km² with a population of almost 1.63 million. The Eastern Slovak region borders with Ukraine on the eastern side, Hungary on the southern side and Poland on the northern side (sodbtn.sk, 2023).

Figure 1 East Slovak region map (Author with 3bodky.webnode.cz, 2012)

The solutions of Eastern Slovakia region's ITS were not already implemented. The implementation of this system has been suspended in the whole region but some measures in the field of rail and bus transport have been implemented. These are mainly changing in timetables in rail transport, i.e. increase in transport availability and changes in transport lines or reduction of parallel rides (PR) in bus transport. The changes also involve the Košice - Prešov route. PR decrease the efficiency of public transport and cause unnecessary, purposeless production of greenhouse gases and increase of external and operating costs (University of Žilina, 2020).

In fact, in spite of all the changes, there are still simultaneous operations of railway and bus transport on the Košice - Prešov line, especially regional express trains (REx) and express bus connections running on the motorway parallel to the railway line. Mentioned buses lines directly connect cities Košice and Prešov by the similar way as a REx trains, with the same purpose and in some cases at the same time. Both connection alternatives are relatively similar from the passenger's perspective in terms of travel time, boarding location and route. Therefore, parallel connections of bus and rail transport on this route may not ensure synergistic effect in transport, which is one of the main conditions for efficient management of public transport and ITS (Lakatos, 2020).

The aim of the reduction and ITS is to ensure the purposefulness of the transport performance provided in each mode of public transport. The railway line Košice - Prešov - Plaveč is electrified and therefore rail transport is eco-friendlier than transport by buses with combustion engines. The reduction will transfer the performance to the eco-friendlier system of faithful transport, which has a major carrier character in the region. The saved performance of bus transport can be used as a complement to rail transport so that synergies are created while maintaining the efficiency and turnover of bus transport will be preserve (Nedeliaková, 2019).

The purpose of the paper is to find out the answers on questions whether the reduction of PR on the Košice - Prešov relation will bring benefits in terms of the environmental impact of commuting on this relation and whether it is possible to quantify or express these benefits in numerical terms at all. The goal is a quantitative evaluation of the reduction in terms of the saved transport performance, saved the amount of GHGs, the external costs incurred in the production of GHGs and footprint comparison as well as demonstration of reduction benefits.

1. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Relevant sources of information in the field of PR, public transport and green house gases emmissions will be cited in this part of the article.

1.1. LITERATURE REVIEW

Research by Clark, at al. (2003) indicates that as the distance or commute time between the household and the destination (work, school, other) increases, the transport flows along a given route are decreased.

Parallel rides of rail and transport can significantly reduce the efficiency of public transport in the region. Reducing parallel journeys can increase the efficiency of transport by reducing its operating costs, increasing revenues and also by reducing the negative environmental impacts of commuting. The authors Kudláč, et al. (2017) argue that the quality of public transport by reducing PR should not be decreased at all or only minimally.

The authors Bastos, et al., (2019) have shown that commuting has a negative impact on the environment and the production of green-house gases. In particular, commuting by internal combustion engine vehicles. However, according to Kaushik, et al. (2018), transportation provided by electric vehicles is eco-friendly only if some part of the electricity is generated otherwise than by fossil fuels

Better coordination of public transport can boost the satisfaction of passengers, transport operators or performance contracting authorities. Also, it helps with making the public transport more eco-friandly. In addition, the attractiveness of the region itself may increase not only for local citizens but also in terms of truism and recreation (Ren, 2020).

1.2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF PARALLEL RIDES

Parallel transport or rides means regular public transport services (e.g. bus transport) which routes are identical or similar to another or the same public passenger transport mode (e.g. rail transport) by routing of routes and timings in timetables. PR can be considered as services on the same route with a separation of departures from stops or stations less than 1,500 m apart within a time range of ± 30 minutes (Mesto Žilina, 2021).

In the case of this article, reduction of PR does not only mean termination of the reduced connections, but also their modification, i.e., for example, coordination with rail transport so

that given bus services will be complementary to rail transport or given services will be used on other lines. This modification should help to achieve higher efficiency (Gasparik, 2018)

Green-house gases (GHG) are gases that are responsible for the greenhouse effect, which may be the cause of the current global warming. One of the main sources of GHGs is industry and transport, approximately 65%, as there is extensive use of fossil fuels in this sphere (Kuang, 2021).

The most prominent greenhouse gases produced by transport include carbon dioxide CO₂, carbon monoxide CO, methane CH₄ and nitrogen oxide N₂O (Kuang, 2021).

Emission factor - represents the amount of GHG emitted into the air when 1 kg of fossil fuel is burned, or how much GHG is attributed to the consumption of one kWh of electricity (Lee, 2014).

CBA is a methodical handbook and manual for cost-benefit analysis in the framework of investment projects within the transport sector. The elaborated CBA is a basis for applicants of co-financing projects in the transport sector through the Operational Programme Integrated Infrastructure 2014-2020 (MDaV SR, 2021) & (Tol, 2012).

Regional and inter-regional transport, as defined by the UITP, is used to transport passengers from lower population areas and suburban areas to local centers; it can also provide transport between local centers that are only a short distance apart (UITP, 2013).

Zonal - operation transport services represent a regional public transport service, with operation similar to long-distance services along part or whole of the route. For example, between major centers of a region. Vehicles stop only at major stations to provide a faster service in regional and inter-regional traffic (Dedík, 2019).

The deployment of ITS within a geographical area should improve the quality and efficiency of local public transport by unifying, cooperating and coordinating the different involved transport modes. The increase in the quality and efficiency of public transport will not only be recognized by passengers but also by transport operators and performance contracting authorities (Gregova, 2014).

External costs - also known as society-wide costs - can be understood as the activities of an enterprise that cause costs to other parties (enterprises, population, environment, etc.) without being compensated. GHG emissions are one of the external costs (Hinš, 2006).

2.DATA AND METHODOLOGY

In order to identify and verify the impacts resulting from the reduction of parallel bus and rail transport on the Košice - Prešov route, it will be necessary to characterise the monitored transport section and collect the most important data, which will be used according to the methodological procedure to obtain the results.

2.1. CHARACTERISTICS OF RELEVANT ROUTE

The route on which we are dealing with the problem of parallel rides connects the 2 largest cities in the eastern Slovak region. These cities are connected by the railway line number 188 Košice - Prešov - Lipany - Plaveč and several parallel roads. For example, the first class roads I/20, I/68 and D1 motorway (Handzuš, 2023). Regional buses, long-distance connections and also express zonal-operation bus lines run on these roads.

The railway line is currently served mainly by regional trains. These are zone - operating trains (regional-express trains) and classic stopping commuter trains. Regional express trains (REx) provide high-capacity services and commuter trains and bus services should complement them. Rail transport in this region forms a backbone transport network (Handzuš, 2023).

REx trains connect Košice and Prešov directly with only one intermediate stop in the Kysak interchange station. The travel time by these trains on the section Košice - Prešov is 31 minutes and length is 33 km, which is similar to travelling by express buses running on the D1 motorway, i.e. 30 minutes and 34 km. Mentioned buses lines directly connect cities Košice and Prešov by the similar way as a REx trains, with the same purpose and in some cases at the “semi-same” time. In this case, parallel runs of REx trains and express buses are formed. In this case, parallel runs of REx trains and express buses are created. Both of these road variants connect the main bus and railway stations in Košice and Prešov, which are in the same location (University of Žilina, 2020).

All train and some bus connections continue on their way but it is the location of the stations that will allow a seamless transfer also in connection with the implementation of ITS. By removing the parallel rides of the express bus and REx trains on this route, the potential of the electrified line could be better utilized.

2.2. BASIC INPUT DATA TO THE SOLVING OF THE PROBLEM OF PARALLEL RIDES

The following Table 1 lists the most important input variables for solving the problem of parallel rides and saving emissions when reducing them. The variables resources in Slovak conditions are several documents, particularly CBA analysis, Transport Service Plan of Prešov region, university of Žilina, etc.

Tab. 1 Input variables for evaluation

Variable	Description	Value	Reference
L_B	Transport length by Bus	34 km	University of Zilina, 2020
L_T	Transport length by Train	33 km	
n_E	Number of EMU	1	VOD časť 3, 2022
n_S	Number of train sets	5	
N_T	Total number of vehicles	6	
C_E	Unit consumption of EMU	9.9 kWh*trainkm ⁻¹	MDaV SR, 2021
C_S	Unit consumption of train sets	12.8 kWh*trainkm ⁻¹	
C_{BU}	Unit diesel consumption of bus (in 0,82 kg/dm ³)	0.92 l*km ⁻¹ or 0,24 kg*km ⁻¹	
c_E	Capacity of EMU	343 seatplaces	VOD časť 3, 2022
c_S	Capacity of train sets	452 seatplaces	
M_E	Mass of EMU	159.5 t	
M_S	Mass of train set	302 t	
M_H	Mass of human	0.08 t	University of Zilina, 2020
Φ_{OCB}	Average occupancy of a bus	21 passengers	
Φ_{OCT}	Average occupancy of train in % on line 188	45 %	
E_{FCO_2}	Emmision factors of CO ₂	3,140 g*kg ⁻¹	MDaV SR, 2021
E_{FCH_4}	Emmision factors of CH ₄	0.27 g*kg ⁻¹	
E_{FN_2O}	Emmision factors of N ₂ O	0.051 g*kg ⁻¹	
$E_{FE_{CO_2}}$	Emmision factors of CO ₂ for electric energy	210 g*kWh ⁻¹	
P_{CO_2}	1 tone price of CO ₂	140.6 €*t ⁻¹	
k_{CH_4}	equivalent of CO ₂ -> CH ₄	25	
K_{N_2O}	equivalent of CO ₂ -> N ₂ O	298	

Some of the variables will need to be averaged, because 2 vehicles with different parameters are used to operate REx trains in a ratio of 1:5 (VOD časť 3, 2022). We will need to recalculate the tabulated values using a weighted average to obtain the average outcome variable.

Specifically, the average electricity consumption of train C_T (1), average capacity of trains c_T (2), average weight of train M_T (3).

$$C_T = \frac{n_E * C_E + n_S * C_S}{N_T} = 12,32 \text{ kWh} * \text{traikm}^{-1} \quad (1)$$

$$c_T = \frac{n_E * c_E + n_S * c_S}{N_T} = 434 \text{ seatplaces} \quad (2)$$

$$M_T = \frac{n_E * M_E + n_S * M_S}{N_T} = 278,25 \text{ t} \quad (3)$$

We use the values calculated through the previous relations and other values from the table to calculate the brutto mass of the train M_B , i.e. the occupied train by passengers (4) and the energy consumption for the mass of 1 passenger C_p by using direct proportionality (5)

$$M_B = M_T + M_H * \Phi O c_T * c_T = 293,87 \text{ t} \quad (4)$$

$$C_p = \frac{C_T * M_H}{M_B} = 0,0034 \text{ kWh} * \text{trainkm}^{-1} \quad (5)$$

All these values will later be essential in the performance and GHG savings calculations thanks to the reduction of parallel rides.

2.3. METODOLOGICAL PROCEDURE FOR EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF THE REDUCTION OF PARALLEL RIDES ON ROUTE KOŠICE – PREŠOV

The methodological procedure for evaluating the impact of reducing parallel rides can be divided into 2 parts. The first-part is the methodology for determining the PR and the saved operational performance (OP). Second part deals with the particular benefits of the reduction, e.i. saved emissions of GHG, its external costs and a comparison of carbon footprint. The specific procedure for solving the first part (Fig. 2) and the second part (Fig. 3) is depicted within the flowcharts.

Reduction of parallel rides

Once the PR conditions have been defined and the baseline data collected, the first step is to determine the PR themselves and their number. The studied rides must agree with the route and line under study. Transport timetables can be a useful tool and it should be exposed in graph. The second step is the calculation of saved operational performance of bus transport thanks to the PR's reduction, the annual value in this case. Not least is determination of new passengers whose transfer from terminated bus connection to railway transport. The procedure is shown in the following flowchart (Fig. 2).

Figure 2 Flowchart - Reduction of PR

Relations for the calculation of bus OP saved thanks to PR's reduction:

$$\begin{aligned}
 OP_w &= L_B * Np_w \\
 OP_f &= L_B * Np_f \\
 OP_y &= OP_w * d_w + OP_f * d_f
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

$OP_{w/f}$ – Saved operational performance per works' day/free day

$Np_{w/f}$ – Number of PR per works' day/free day

$d_{w/f}$ – Number of works' day/free day per year

OP_y – Total saved OP of bus transport per year

Relation for the calculation of new rail passengers - NP_y . We have made an expert estimate that 70% of the passengers on the reduced services will transfer to rail services.

$$NP_y = (Np_w * d_w + Np_f * d_f) * \Phi Oc_B * 70\% \tag{7}$$

Benefits of reduction of parallel rides

The benefits of the reduction of parallel rides are understood in this article as the GHG emissions saved from the saved operation performance and the operation performance of the bus operators itself, which can be used for other purpose as well as saved useless external cost and expected carbon footprint change. The specific procedure for calculating the benefits is represented by the second process chart (Fig. 3) and the following sets of relations.

Figure 3 Flowchart – Quantification of PR's benefits reduction

The supporting methodology for calculating the saved emissions, saved external costs and for the carbon footprint will be the CBA methodology. The aim of these calculations is to quantitatively demonstrate the benefits of the PR reductions addressed in this paper.

Formulas for the determination of emissions of individual GHGs produced by a single bus journey on the route Košice - Prešov are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{CO_2} &= \frac{E_{FCO_2} * C_B * L_B}{1000} \\
 E_{CH_4} &= \frac{E_{FCO_2} * C_B * L_B}{1000} \\
 E_{N_2O} &= \frac{E_{FN_2O} * C_B * L_B}{1000}
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Calculation of emissions in the context of annual power saved:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{CO_2y} &= \frac{E_{FCO_2} * C_B * OP_y}{1000000} \\
 E_{CH_4/N_2Oy} &= \frac{E_{FN_2O/CH_4} * C_B * OP_y}{1000}
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

The correction of the saved CO2 emissions by the increased electricity consumption of the train due to the increase of its occupancy by NP_y. For other emissions this value is negligible.

$$E_{CO2y}^* = E_{CO2y} - \frac{C_p * NP_y * E_{EFCO2}}{1000000} \quad (10)$$

Formulas for calculating annual external cost savings resulting from annual performance are showed there:

$$\begin{aligned} SC_{CO2} &= E_{CO2y}^* * P_{CO2} \\ SC_{CH4/N2O} &= \frac{E_{CH4/N2Oy}}{1000} * P_{CO2} * k_{CH4/N2O} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The total saved annual GHGs' external costs:

$$SC = SC_{CO2} + SC_{CH4} + SC_{N2O} \quad (12)$$

Following relations are calculation of the carbon footprint of one bus and rail passenger (including NP_y). This is the calculation of carbon footprint per single ride.

$$\begin{aligned} CF_B &= \frac{E_{CO2}}{\Phi O c_B} \\ CF_T &= \frac{L_T * (C_T + \Phi O c_B * 70\% * C_p) * \frac{E_{FCO2}}{1000}}{\frac{C_T}{2} + \Phi O c_B * 70\%} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

The achieved values will have to be compared between each other. The desired result is that the carbon footprint of a single passenger of rail transport is lower than the carbon footprint of bus transport in the same conditions.

3.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Primarily it is necessary to create a study of the existing PR within the case study on the Košice - Prešov relation. Subsequently, from the obtained results of the study and other input data available in Chapter 2, it will be possible to present the achieved benefits of the reduction on the addressed relation.

3.1. PARALLEL RIDES OF BUS AND RAIL TRANSPORT ON ROUTE KOŠICE – PREŠOV

Parallel rides of railway and bus transport on route Košice – Prešov – (Lipany – Muszyna) arise in several cases, but in this article, we have focused on the PR of REx trains and express bus connections running on the D1 motorway between these cities. These are regional express bus services operating on the aforementioned route with departures within ± 15 min of the REx trains departure from the same station. In our case the PR is within ± 15 minutes instead of ± 30 minutes (inspiration is ITS in Žilina region). Reason for reducing this value are to the strong traffic flows on the route (NDCon s.r.o, 2019). The reduction of PR does not include long-distance and international bus connections.

The graph in Fig. 1 shows the number of PR over the working (green and blue points) and free day (red and yellow points) in both the even (below the y-axis) and odd (above the y-axis) directions. The PR are related to the pair of train connections, i.e. the values on the x-axis.

Figure 4 Number of PR between Košice and Prešov, (Author via CHAPS, 2023)

The graph shows that more PR occur during the working days. Based on the analysis of the timetables, this can be explained by the fact that there are more connections in both modes of transport during working days. The graph also shows an unevenness in the number of PR by direction of travel, especially the number of PR occurring on free days. Overall, 20 PR occur in the even direction on a working day and 2 on a free day, and 18 PR occur in the odd direction on a weekday and 10 on a free day.

3.2. SAVED OPERATIONAL PERFORMANCE

With the reduction of PR plotted in Fig. 1, it is possible to save a significant number of OPs in just one day without compromising the quality of the public transport service. Table 2 describes the saved traffic performance in vkm from the reduction of PR on the Košice - Prešov route for each type of day and for the total per year based on relations (6).

$$\begin{aligned}
 OP_w &= 34 * 38 = 1,292 \text{ vkm} \\
 OP_f &= 34 * 12 = 408 \text{ vkm} \\
 OP_y &= 1\,292 * 247 + 408 * 118 = \mathbf{367,268 \text{ vkm}}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{6}$$

Tab. 2 Saved operational performance

Transport direction	Number of PR		Saved OP per day		Total saved OP per work's days	Total saved OP per free days	Number of work's days	Number of free days	Total saved annual OP
	Work's days	Free days	Work's days	Free days					
	[#PR]	[#PR]	[vkm]	[vkm]	[vkm]	[vkm]	[days]	[days]	[vkm]
Even direction	20	2	680	68	1.292	408	247	118	367,268
Odd direction	18	10	612	340					

The bus transport performance (367,268 vkm) saved through the reduction of PR can be used in other ways, e.g.:

- by modifying the timing of the reduced services so that they are not parallel but complementary to the REx trains;
- use of performance on other lines, reinforcement of service availability on other routes;
- change of a departure time,
- a simple saving of power and the run of vehicles;
- and other options.

3.3. SAVED EMISSIONS OF GREEN HOUSE GASES

The quantities of GHG – CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O emissions saved per reduced one PR in kg calculated from relationships (8) are shown below.

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{CO_2} &= \frac{3\,140 * 0.24 * 34}{1000} = 25.224 \text{ kg} \\
 E_{CH_4} &= \frac{0.27 * 0.24 * 34}{1000} = 0.022 \text{ kg} \\
 E_{N_2O} &= \frac{0.051 * 0.24 * 34}{1000} = 0.0042 \text{ kg}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{8}$$

Within Fig. 5, these values are represented graphically in a chart.

Figure 5: The mass of saved GHG per reduced 1 ride

For the reduction of one ride of an express bus on the route Košice - Prešov, it will save 25.6224 kg of CO₂. Other gases are saved only a negligible amount compared to CO₂, but these gases generate a stronger greenhouse effect (Kuang, 2021).

In case of reduction of all PR outlined in the graph (Fig. 3) per one year of operation, the amount of emission of CO₂ in tons and CH₄ and N₂O emissions in kg will be saved. Particular values should be met by formulas (9).

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{CO_2y} &= \frac{3,140 * 0.24 * 367,268}{1000000} = 276,773 \text{ t} \\
 E_{CH_4y} &= \frac{0.27 * 0.24 * 367,268}{1000} = 23,799 \text{ kg} \\
 E_{N_2Oy} &= \frac{0.051 * 0.24 * 367\,268}{1000} = 4,495 \text{ kg}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{9}$$

The amount of CO₂ emissions saved is discounted by the additional emissions resulting from the increased electricity consumption of the train due to new passengers travelling by rail (10), of whom there are 158 789 according to formula (7).

$$NP_y = (38 * 247 + 12 * 118) * 21 * 70\% = 158,789 p \quad (7)$$

$$E_{CO_2y}^* = E_{CO_2y} - \frac{0.0034 * 158,789 * 210}{10000000} = 276.66 t \quad (10)$$

The following chart (Fig. 6) shows the total amount of saved emissions by the reduction of parallel rides, whereby every gas is presented in tonas. Addition of train emission is presented by orange colour.

Figure 6: The mass of saved GHGs per yer

As in the chart above, the most dominant annual emissions saved are CO₂ emissions, and the addition of new passengers to the train's emissions is only minimal, approx. 1/10 of a tonne.

3.4. SAVED EXTERNAL COSTS OF GREEN HOUSE GAS EMISSIONS

Based on the formulas (11) mentioned in methodologies, the price of the external costs that are produced through the emission of individual GHGs are calculated.

$$\begin{aligned}
 SC_{CO_2} &= 276,66 * 140.6 = 38\,898.40 \text{ €} \\
 SC_{CH_4} &= \frac{23,799}{1000} * 140.6 * 25 = 83.65 \text{ €} \\
 SC_{SH_4/N_2O} &= \frac{4,495}{1000} * 140.6 * 298 = 188.34 \text{ €}
 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The total cost of the annual external costs that will be saved after the reduction of the specified PR shown in Fig. 1 is represented by relation (12)

$$SC = 38\,898,40 \text{ €} + 83,65 \text{ €} + 188,34 \text{ €} = \mathbf{39,170.39 \text{ €}} \quad (12)$$

The following chart (Fig. 7) is a graphical representation of the ratio of saved external costs. The graph includes saved external cost of all dealt GH gases.

Figure 7: The price of saved GHGs external cost per yer

The total amount of external costs saved is 39,170.39 €, with carbon dioxide costs accounting for the largest part, followed by methane and finally nitrous oxide.

3.5. COMPARISON OF CARBON FOOTPRINT

Based on the formulas (13) presented in Chapter 2, the carbon footprint of a passenger using bus transport and rail transport is calculated. The resulting values are compared.

$$CF_B = \frac{25.224}{21} = 1.201 \text{ kg}$$

$$CF_T = \frac{33 * (0,0034 + 21 * 70\%) * 12.32 * \frac{210}{1000}}{\frac{434}{2} + 21 * 70\%} = 0.369 \text{ kg} \quad (13)$$

0.369 kg (train) < 1.201 kg (bus)

The results demonstrate that the utilization of rail transport on the Košice - Prešov route instead of bus transport also reduces the carbon footprint of the passenger in making this journey.

3.6. DISCUSSION

The traffic service plan of the Prešov and Košice self-governing region prepared by University of Žilina, (2020) also dealt with the problematic of PR in the surroundings of the line section Košice - Prešov - Lipany, but it focused especially on PR occurring on parallel roads in immediate distance from the railway line, for example I/68, I/20, road 3390, etc.

The paper uses many of the average input values available in CBA analysis rather than values derived from real operating conditions on a particular line. Real values could partially differ from the averages. However, for the purposes of this case study, these values are adequate and it may be possible to conduct this study in more detail in the future with the real values from the operation of the vehicles on the Košice – Prešov line.

The amount of CO₂ and other GHGs saved in this way is only a tiny fraction of the amount that is unnecessarily produced per year in the whole Slovak Republic or the World (enviro portal, 2023) & (Porter, 2018).

The reduced bus connections do not reflect real vehicle circulation, neither does it define how the efficiency of the bus service will be ensured after the reduction. The paper only proposes some solutions, such as changing departure times, using available buses on different routes, shortening routes, etc. (see 3.2). In case of shortening the lines only to the interchange stations (Košice or Prešov), many passengers will have to transfer between train and bus. This will require the implementation of a unified tariff, which will be appreciated by daily commuters because of the prepaid cheaper fare as well as to ensure ideal connectivity (Rodrigue, 2020).

In the event that parallel services are not directly terminated, but modified, these emissions will be produced more efficiently than with services that are parallel to other eco-friendlier transport modes (Ližbetinová, 2021).

The author of an article in the Vlaky.net portal (“Trains.net”), argues about the need to reduce the parallel rides of bus and railway transport in the Nitra region. This is the cancellation or modification of parallel bus services, which falls under the public obligation services. The aim of such a reduction would be to increase the transport availability of the area, to make the transport services more efficient and to ensure sufficient utilisation of the means of transport (Engler, 2011).

CONCLUSION

The paper deals with a case study of the reduction of parallel rides of railway and bus transport between the city Košice and Prešov, which is carried out by express connections. The problematic, parallel, connections were selected on the basis of the valid 2022/2023 timetables according to the specifications defined in the text of the article. The aim of the paper was to demonstrate the benefits of PR reduction in the field of saved operational performance, emissions, external costs as well as to compare the carbon footprint of the compared modes of transport.

The proposed reductions of PR on the Košice - Prešov route in this article are in favour of rail transport, due to the benefit coming from its electrification. In parallel, we have transferred the performance of vehicles with internal combustion engine - buses to rail transport, which produces significantly lower emissions. On the basis of the research developed in this paper, we have determined the amount of saved purposeless transport power, the weight of saved greenhouse gas emissions and the consequent external costs.

By reducing PR on a focused route, we can save approximately 367,000 vkm per year. Part of these performances will be possible to modify and use more practically or efficiently, for example by enhancing bus transport services in locations where the services are not adequate or to ensure a change of bus transport timetables on the Košice - Prešov route to make it complementary to rail transport, which should also be assisted by ITS, which should be introduced in the region.

The saved transport performance will also bring with it a saving in the purposeless production of GHG emissions, which are produced when fossil fuels are burned in bus engines. In particular, of the 367,000 vkm saved, 276.66 t of carbon dioxide, 23.8 kg of methane and 4,5 kg of nitrous oxide will be saved. In addition to saving pollution, this will also save external costs of GHGs pollution amounting to almost 40,000€. Taktiež ak cestujúci zvolí na danej trase železničnú dopravu namiesto autobusovej zníži aj svoju uhlíkovú stopu z prepravy medzi Prešovom s Košicami.

For real practical application, it will be appropriate to apply the study more precisely by using real input values. The study can also be applied to other localities where PR is occurring and thus reduce the negative environmental impacts of transport elsewhere.

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REFERENCES

Clark, W. A. V., Huang, Y., & Withers, S. (2003). Does commuting distance matter? *Regional Science and Urban Economics*, 33, 199–221. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0166-0462\(02\)00012-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0166-0462(02)00012-1)

Kudláč, Š., Majerčák, J., & Mańkowski, C. (2017). The proposal of coordination the rail and bus passenger transport on the relation žilina – ružomberok. *Procedia Engineering*, 192, 510–515. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2017.06.088>

Bastos, J., Marques, P., Batterman, S. A., & Freire, F. (2018). Environmental impacts of commuting modes in lisbon: A life-cycle assessment addressing particulate matter impacts on health. *International Journal of Sustainable Transportation*, 13(9), 652–663. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15568318.2018.1501519>

Kaushik, H., Mathew, M., & Hossain, J. (2018). Comparative analysis of Green House gas emission from different vehicular fuels. 2018 International Conference on Power Energy, Environment and Intelligent Control (PEEIC). <https://doi.org/10.1109/peeic.2018.8665618>

Ren, G., & Ouyang, Y. (2020). Coordinated passenger flow control and bus connection setting during peak hour of Urban Rail Transit. *ICTE 2019*. <https://doi.org/10.1061/9780784482742.011>

Bastos, J., Marques, P., Batterman, S. A., & Freire, F. (2018). Environmental impacts of commuting modes in lisbon: A life-cycle assessment addressing particulate matter impacts on health. *International Journal of Sustainable Transportation*, 13(9), 652–663. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15568318.2018.1501519>

Kuang, C. (2021). Analysis of green house gases and positive impact of replacing traditional energy with Clean Energy. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 241, 02005. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202124102005>

Jean-Paul Rodrigue (2020), New York: Routledge, 456 pages. ISBN 978-0-367-36463-2

Dedík, M., Čechovič, T., Gašparík, J., & Majerčák, J. (2019). Rationalization of the passenger transport system as an important transport system. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 40, 193–200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2019.07.030>

UITP, International Association of Public Transport. (2013). Demographic changes and challenges for regional transport (Core brief). Brussels: Author

LEE, K. M., & LEE, M. H. (2021). Uncertainty of the electricity emission factor incorporating the uncertainty of the fuel emission factors. *Energies*, 14(18), 5697.

Gregova, E., & Dengova, E. (2014). 2014 2ND INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON SOCIAL SCIENCES RESEARCH. In *Advances in Social and Behavioral Sciences* (1st ed., Vol. 5, pp. 20–25). Hong Kong.

Mesto Žilina. (2021). Návrh plánu dopravnej obsluhy (obslužnosti) hromadnou osobnou dopravou mesta Žilina. Žilina, Slovakia.

MDaV SR. (2021). Metodická príručka k tvorbe analýz nákladov a prínosov (CBA) verzia 3.0. Bratislava, Slovakia.

Tol, R. S. J. (2012). A cost–benefit analysis of the EU 20/20/2020 package. *Energy Policy*, 49, 288–295. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2012.06.018>

Greenhouse gas emissions. enviro portal. (n.d.). Retrieved January 27, 2023, from <https://www.enviroportal.sk/indicator/detail?id=1745>

Porter, S. D., Reay, D. S., Bomberg, E., & Higgins, P. (2018). Avoidable food losses and associated production-phase greenhouse gas emissions arising from application of cosmetic standards to fresh fruit and vegetables in Europe and the UK. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 201, 869–878. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.08.079>

Plán udržateľnej mobility Prešovského samosprávneho kraja, NDCon s.r.o., 2019.

University of Žilina. (2020). Plán dopravnej obslužnosti Prešovského samosprávneho kraja. Žilina, Slovakia. from: <https://www.po-kraj.sk/sk/samosprava/kompetencie-psk/doprava/pdo-psk/>

Gasparik, J., Dedič, M., Dlugos, M., & Zahumenska, Z. (2018). Development of rail passenger transport by optimizing the operational and organizational measures. *International conference on traffic and transport engineering (ictte 2018)*, 628–634.

Ližbetinová, L., Lejsková, P., Nedeliaková, E., Caha, Z., & Hitka, M. (2021). The growing importance of ecological factors to employees in the transport and logistics sector. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 35(1), 4379–4403.

Hinšt, Z. (2006, November 24). European studies on external costs of Transport. *Ekonomski pregled*. Retrieved February 6, 2023, from <https://hrcak.srce.hr/clanak/12968>

CHAPS spol. s.r.o. (n.d.). Cestovné Poriadky CP.SK. CP. Retrieved February 6, 2023, from <https://cp.hnonline.sk/vlakbus/spojenie/?x=1675677748458>

Nedeliaková, E., Štefancová, V., & Hranický, M. P. (2019). Implementation of Six sigma methodology using DMAIC to achieve processes improvement in Railway Transport. *Production Engineering Archives*, 23(23), 18–21. <https://doi.org/10.30657/pea.2019.23.03>

Lakatos, A., & Mándoki, P. (2020). Mode-choice analysis in long-distance, parallel public transport. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 44, 332–341.

Engler, M. (2011, July 12). Vlak Alebo Autobus? VLAKY.NET. Retrieved February 14, 2023, from <https://www.vlaky.net/zeleznice/spravy/4066-Vlak-alebo-autobus/>

VOD časť 3, 2022, Bratislava: Železničná spoločnosť, a.s.

Handzuš, J. 2023. The proposal of changing railway transfer points in the area of the city of Prešov [Diploma thesis]. University of Žilina. Faculty of Operation and Economics of transport and Communications; Department of Railway transport. Žilina: FPEDAS, ŽU, 2023. 83 pages.

3bodky.webnode.cz, 2012. *3 bodky Edity, Mišky a Lenky*. [online] <https://3bodky.webnode.cz/spajame-vychod/>

OBCE SR - sodbtn.sk. (n.d.). Retrieved April 21, 2023, from <http://sodbtn.sk/obce/>